

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR ANALYSES OF PLASTICS UNDER ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES

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1 Introduction

The mechanical behaviours of engineering plastics are significantly influenced by environmental changes. For automobile applications, the plastic structures for dashboard, instruments and other panels are continuously exposed to sun lights and moisture, which lead to substantial changes of material properties. The physical and mechanical property changes of polymeric materials are due to their unique amorphous molecular structure, and categorized as physical aging and degradation [1, 2]. Many literatures are available on the aging phenomena, and it is known that the behaviour stems from thermodynamic equilibrium process. The memory effects under T_g is erased and recovered (rejuvenated) when the material experiences the temperature above T_g [3-8]. On the other hand, degradation is not well defined and commonly used as same as physical aging. However, degradation distinguishes itself as irreversible process due to permanent changes of the molecular structures, which may be induced by moisture, oxygen, ultraviolet light and chemical attacks. In the material characterizations, however, it is not easy task to separate these two phenomena from each other [9-11]. The significance of the physical aging and degradation exists on the fact that those induce remarkable mechanical and physical properties change. In automobile applications, the material property changes substantially impact the mechanical functions of plastic fixtures. Fasteners and clips lose their structural rigidities, creating unexpected functional problems such as noise. To prevent Buzz, Squeak and Rattle (BSR) noises in the initial design stage, it is critical to analyze, understand and predict the mechanical properties under temperature, humidity as well as time. In this study, the mechanical property changes of thermoplastics for automobile applications are

measured to investigate the environmental effects on the material behaviours. Three popular engineering plastics for automobiles, ABS, ABS+Polycarbonate (ABS+PC) and Polypropylene with an amount of reinforcing fibers (PPF) are chosen for the study. The samples were undergone thermal as well as moisture absorption conditionings, and the mechanical properties such as Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, glass transition temperature, coefficient of thermal expansion were periodically measured. The storage and loss modulus for viscoelastic characteristics were also examined. The data are compared with the reference (fresh) samples, and the trends of the properties change are studied.

2 Tests and Results

2.1 Weight changes by moisture absorption

Before the tests, moisture absorption of the samples were tested. The samples were placed in a dryer and undergone 60°C for 7 hours to remove the moisture, and then moved in the hygro-thermal chamber for the moisture absorption treatment under 85% relative humidity at 82.5°C. The samples were taken out periodically, and the weights were measured. The results are shown in Fig 1. As seen, the moisture absorptions of ABS+PC and PPF reached at the maximum in about one day, and ABS took about one and half days. The results also show ABS absorb the moisture much more than the other two materials, about 0.8% maximum by weight ratio.

2.2 Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio

Young's modulus and Poisson's ratios at room temperature were measured after the thermal and moisture conditionings. The conditions for the moisture were the same as that of the weight change analyses by the moisture absorption in the previous section, and the temperature for the isothermal treatment was 82.5°C. The thermal cycles were

designed to jump the temperatures between -40°C and 85°C . The dwell time at each temperature was two hours, meaning that six cycles were completed in a day. The samples were taken out at 10, 15, 20, 42 and 56 days after the treatments. The treatment conditions were kept identical for the entire mechanical properties change measurements. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were measured based on ASTM D638. Five samples were used for each measurement case. Fig 2-5 show the Young's modulus changes of the materials by average values and standard deviations. The results represent that PPF demonstrated noticeable decrease of the average modulus, while ABS+PC almost same within the error range. On the other hand, when the PPF samples were treated under the isothermal condition, the modulus was increased. Similarity was found from ABS, although the trend was relatively weak. For the ABS+PC case, little change was found. In the case of the thermal cycling, the modulus of PPF was decreased, while ABS showed slight decrease to 42 days, and increase afterward. Again, ABS+PC did not show any noticeable changes. The results indicated that the moisture and isothermal effects were significant on the PPF modulus changes. ABS also showed similar patterns of the modulus changes with PPF, however, the trend was weak. The results also indicated that the temperature and the moisture effects were minimal on ABS+PC. The changes of Poisson's ratios are also included in the Figures. As seen, the PPF Poisson's ratio was slightly decreased under the isothermal and thermal cycle conditionings. Otherwise, the data showed little changes depending on the conditionings.

Fig.1. Weight changes of the materials by the moisture absorption..

2.3 Coefficient of thermal expansion

The coefficients of thermal expansion were measured by a thermal mechanical analyzer (TA Q400), and the results are represented in Fig. 5. The temperature was increased from -50°C to 100°C at the rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Due to relatively short test time, the moisture contents variation in the samples during the tests were assumed to be minor. As seen, the CTE of ABS showed slight decrease when the samples were treated under isothermal condition and the thermal cycling. The PPF data represented much higher values than the other materials in rather scattering pattern, and no discernable trends were found. ABS+PC showed relatively constant values.

Fig.2. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio changes of the materials by the humidity conditioning.

Fig.3. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio changes of the materials by the isothermal conditioning.

Fig.4. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio changes of the materials by the thermal cycle conditioning.

Fig. 5. The changes of the coefficients of thermal expansion of the materials.

Fig. 6. Dynamic mechanical analyses of the fresh samples to measure the glass transition temperatures.

Fig. 7. The changes of the glass transition temperatures of the materials depending on the environmental conditionings.

2.4 Glass transition temperature

Glass transition temperatures were measured by a dynamic mechanical analyzer (TA 2980) using single cantilever mode under 1Hz. The temperature was increased by 5°C/min from room temperature. The results of the storage modulus, loss modulus and $\tan \delta$ of the fresh samples are illustrated in Fig. 6. The glass transition temperatures were measured at the peak of $\tan \delta$. The temperatures of ABS and ABS+PC were found to be 128°C and about 141°C, respectively. For PPF, perceivable peak was found at

about 20°C. The temperature changes depending on the conditionings are represented in Fig. 7. The results demonstrated the glass transition temperatures of ABS+PC and PPF were decreased as the time of the sample conditionings was longer. For the case of ABS, the trend of the temperature change was not clearly defined.

Fig. 8. Storage modulus variations of the materials under the temperature and frequency sweep.

Fig. 9. Loss modulus variations of the materials under the temperature and frequency sweep.

2.5 Storage and loss modulus

In the vibration analyses of plastic materials for the noise analyses at high temperature, it is necessary to obtain the storage modulus and loss modulus for viscoelastic analyses. To obtain the modulus, temperature and frequency sweep tests were performed using the DMA. In this paper, the results of the fresh samples are illustrated. For the tests, the temperature was increased as stepwise from -20°C to 130°C, and the frequency was changed from 0.01Hz to 100Hz at each temperature. Fig. 8 represents the storage modulus results of the materials. As seen, the temperature was increased, the storage modulus was decreased. ABS and ABS+PC noticeably show rapid decreases at high temperature ranges, while PPF at low temperature range. The loss modulus changes are shown in Fig. 9. Generally, ABS and

ABS +PC show slight decrease in the low temperature ranges, and increase in the high temperature range. On the other hand, PPF modulus gradually decreases as the temperature increases. Regarding the frequency effects, the storage modulus remains relatively constant under the frequency changes. On the other hand, the loss modulus is slightly increased for ABS and ABS+PC as the frequency increases, and relatively same for PPF. It was interesting to observe that there are peaks at about 50Hz in the temperature range of -5°C to 100°C for ABS and ABS +PC, and -5°C to 40°C for PPF, the reason of which is under investigation.

3 Conclusions

In this paper, preliminary experimental results of the mechanical property changes of the engineering plastics under environmental treatments are reported. Evidentially, the environmental factors noticeably affected the mechanical behaviors of the materials, and the levels of the effects were different depending on the treatment conditions and the materials. For the case of the moisture effects, PPF Young's modulus was noticeably decreased. On the other hand, isothermal temperature treatment rendered the modulus increases of ABS and PPF. Young's modulus of ABS+PC was remained relatively constant. Poisson's ratio, on the other hand, did not changed as much as the modulus in the test time and temperature ranges performed in this study. The coefficient of thermal expansion was measured, and ABS and PPF showed the slight decrease. The glass transition temperatures were also changed depending on the treatments. Through the temperature and frequency sweep tests, the decrease of the storage modulus was clearly demonstrated as the temperature was increased. For the loss modulus, the reverse was found, although the trend was not certain as the storage modulus. The tests are in progress, and further mechanism analyses are planned as more data is available.

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